

Reformation in Administration and Good Governance: A Study of Maharashtra's Initiatives

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Abstract

Good Governance is a fundamental aspect of modern administration which includes the principles of transparency, accountability, rule of laws, responsiveness and citizen participations. The Government of Maharashtra has initiated several initiatives to promote good governance and e-governance in the state. These papers explain the concepts of administrative reform and good governance and highlight the key principle, legal Framework for Good Governance and best practices in implementing e-governance (*Sevakarmi*) initiatives in Maharashtra.

Keywords: Administrative Reform, Principles Good Governance, Sevakarmi Abhiyan, GPR 2.0

Introduction:

Public Administration is a continuous process and this process is carried out through administrative reforms. Therefore, reform called innovative ways in administration. Administrative reforms are related to administrative transformation. This transformation is brought about under the elements of government-administration organization, procedures, and citizen-administration relations. While carrying out administrative reforms, reforms are made according to the situation to respond to the challenges faced by the management of public affairs, the demands of the operating institutions, and the wishes and expectations of the citizens, and an attempt is made to make administrative capacity more comprehensive with the changing times. Administrative reform is a long-term process, and its goal is to prioritize efficiency by making significant changes in public administration, its operation, structure, and functioning. Administrative reform is long term process. 'In public administration reform is a journey rather than a destination¹'.

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According to G. E. Kaiden “Reform is also based on creativity and man should not wait for change to happen; but should try to accelerate improvement through artificial”² Administrative reform has been initiated both in developed and developing countries to promote good governance.

The concepts of Good Governance and citizen centric administration are intimately connected. Citizen centricity with the aim of ensuring citizens welfare and citizens satisfaction. This concept Good Governance apply to all sectors of society, such as the government, legislature, judiciary, media, private sector, and corporate sector, cooperative societies registered under the Societies Registration Act, and duly registered trusts and organizations. The Prime Minister, (Civil Service Day-2007) in this context, had stated: ‘Effective and efficient institutions form the backbone of a successful development and governance process’³. It’s related to good governance. Because the main aim of Good Governance is providing public services effectively, efficiently and equitably to all citizens. Citizens are thus at the core of good governance.

John Healey and Mark Robinson define “Good governance as a high level of organizational effectiveness in policy formulation and implementation, sustainability, and public welfare, particularly in the development of economic policy”⁴. Good governance also implies transparency, accountability, participation, openness, and the rule of law. Good Governance indicates a quality of governance that is equitable, just, accountable, participatory, and people-oriented. Good governance emphasizes the formulation and effective implementation of people-oriented policies. Good governance aims to improve living standards and, through its administrative processes, strives to ensure maximum benefits for the greatest number of people.

Principles of Good Governance

The principles of good governance ensure that every individual has a fair say in the decision-making process and that government responds to the current and future needs of society. It is participatory, consensus-oriented, accountable, transparent, responsive, effective and efficient, just and inclusive, and adheres to the rule of law. The principles of good governance are:

1. Participation: Participation is an important pillar or key principle of good governance. It can be ensured directly some state or central institutions. It provides every individual with the opportunity to voice their opinion in the decisions of the government. Good governance requires civil society to permit its citizens

to participate in the formulation of development policies and strategies. This aspect of governance is essential to expand commitment and support for projects and to improve the quality of their performance.

2. Rule of Law: The rule of law means that the legal framework of a country is implemented without any discrimination. It also means protecting the rights of vulnerable sections of the population. The rule of law means that no one is above the law and all people are equal before the law. While performing their duties, every government official/employee must strictly follow the law, rules and regulations.

3. Transparency: Transparency in government is a precondition for good governance. This means in decisions and their implementation are carried out in accordance with rules and regulations. The principle of transparency ensures that everyone has equal access to information regarding policy or decisions. It means that information is not only easily accessible, but also presented in an easily understandable form through easily accessible media.

4. Strategic Vision: Every government department/organizations must develop a long-term vision. The vision statement should be followed by a short-term mission statement for five years. Furthermore, the mission statement should be properly integrated into Key Result Areas (KRAs), providing annual targets. These KRAs should be closely aligned with the vision and mission statements.

Source: Manual of Good Governance (2022-23), GAD, Government of Maharashtra, p. 17

5. Responsiveness: Good governance requires organizations to provide timely services to all stakeholders. The administration should be responsive and respond promptly to citizen complaints; especially in times of emergency, administrative response should be prompt.

6. Equality and inclusion: The well-being of society depends on all sections of society getting opportunities for welfare or development. For this, it is necessary that all sections of society, especially the most vulnerable, get opportunities to improve their living conditions. All government

departments/organizations should take the initiative to ensure that the benefits of various schemes reach the most vulnerable sections of society.

7. Accountability: The goal of good governance is to improve the well-being of the people, and this cannot happen unless the government is accountable to the people. Government agencies, the private sector, and civil society organizations must be held accountable to public and institutional stakeholders.

8. Effectiveness and Efficiency: Effectiveness refers to achieving government goals and objectives, while efficiency refers to the ability to effectively utilize resources to deliver timely services. Good governance refers to making the best use of available resources and outcomes, while ensuring that processes and institutions meet the needs of society. In the context of good governance, the concept of efficiency also includes sustainable use of natural resources and protection of the environment.

9. Consensus Orientation: This ensures that decisions are made in the best interests of all stakeholders. This ensures that everyone agrees with the decision and that it benefits the entire community.

In short, good governance helps in providing economic, political and social justice, opportunities through the above principles of good governance.

Reformation in Administration and Good Governance Maharashtra's Initiatives:

1) Legal Framework

Several laws have been enacted to ensure the implementation of good governance. Some important laws/rules promoting good governance in Maharashtra are:

1. Maharashtra Right to Public Services Act, 2015
2. Maharashtra Government Servants Regulation of Transfers and Prevention of Delay in Discharge of Official Duties Act, 2005
3. Right to Information Act, 2005
4. Maharashtra Public Records Act, 2005
5. 73rd Constitutional Amendment for empowering Panchayati Raj Institutions.
6. 74th Constitutional Amendment for empowering Urban Local Bodies.
7. Maharashtra Government Office Procedure Manual (1994)
8. Fiscal Responsibility and Budget Management (FRBM)

In addition to these laws, which have been amended from time to time, the Maharashtra Lokayukta and Upa-Lokayukta Act, 1971 and the Prevention of Corruption Act, 1988 can also be mentioned.

2) **Good Governance Steps Taken by Maharashtra Government:**

Similar to NITI Aayog, the Maharashtra government announced the Maharashtra Institution for Transformation (MITRA) through a government resolution dated November 11, 2022. Its goal is to achieve a USD 1 trillion economy for the state of Maharashtra by 2027 and a USD 3.5 trillion economy by 2047. The institution will function as a think-tank.

The State Office Procedure Rules were last updated and published in 1994. To reflect the changes related to the use of information technology, the State Office Procedure Rules have been updated in collaboration with the Department of Administrative Reforms (DARPG), Government of India. The State Government has implemented e-Office from 1 March 2023. More than 35,000 Aaple Sarkar Seva Kendras have been set up in the state to efficiently provide online services like income, caste, birth, age, nationality, domicile, etc. These centres have become very popular and are receiving huge response from the citizens. SARITA: Computerization of offices and entire administration and registration process in the state of Maharashtra. The Department of Registration and Stamp Registration has automated the core functions of the department using ICT. Apart from this, the Government of Maharashtra is prioritizing administrative reforms and innovation through E -Governance, Aaple Sarkar Portal, computerization of land records, Good Governance District Index, Social Audit, Citizen feedback, Sevakarmi Mission, GPR 2.0 etc.

3) **150-day e-Governance Campaign/Service Employees Mission:**

Under this campaign, focusing on three main components namely e-Governance Reforms, Developed Maharashtra 2047 and Service Reforms, the Government of Maharashtra decided to implement Governor Reforms in the offices from the Department Secretariat to the District -*Taluka* level and its evaluation will be done by an external mechanism called Quality Council of India.

This transformation/reform process has 3 pronged strategies which include Government Process Reengineering, Digitization Integrated HR, AI Enabled Systems. A balance of scope and accuracy has been maintained in each of these phases. This program is known as the Service Employees Mission. The main objective of this program was to update the service related matters of officers and employees and to increase efficiency in administrative work. The program was implemented from May 6, 2025 to October 2, 2025 and its evaluation was based on comprehensive issues such as the office's website, *Aaple Sarkar*

system, e-office, office dashboard, WhatsApp Chabot, use of AI and Block chain in government work⁶. After evaluating various administrative departments and corporations participating in the 150-day e-Governance Improvement Program, some of the top/First performing offices is as follows:

Sr. No.	Office name	Rank
1	Collector Office	Jalgoan
2	S P Office	Thane Rural
3	Divisional Commissioner	Nagpur
4	Municipal Corporation	Panvel
5	Ministry	PWD
6	Directorate	Technical Education
7	Police Commissioner	Nashik
8	Nagar Palika	Nilanga

4) Maharashtra Launches 'GPR 2.0'

The Maharashtra government has launched a major administrative reform called "GPR 2.0". Its objective is to bring about significant changes in administration and ensure that the benefits of these reforms reach the people directly. Features of the 'GPR 2.0' initiative of administrative reforms⁷:

Empowerment of administrative departments of the state government:

1. Monitoring through the Chief Minister's Office, Information and Technology Department and the State Information Commissioner's Office for the time-bound implementation of centralized empowerment.
2. Building an efficient system to provide administrative services to the citizens in an easy, convenient and well-organized manner.
3. Preparing a 'Citizen Charter' to ensure easy and quality services to the citizens.
4. Effective and effective implementation of various government schemes implemented for the citizens.

Improvement in service facilities:

1. Improvements have been implemented to make services on the 'MahaDBT' and 'Aaple Sarkar' portals more convenient. 263 schemes under 'MahaDBT 2.0' have been finalized and included in 'GPR 2.0'.
2. Streamlining of 1074 services in 'Aaple Sarkar', as well as better management of 424 standardized services.
3. Selection of centres providing excellent services as 'Smart Centres' out of 17,624 Aaple Sarkar service centres.

Maharashtra is a progressive state and, through numerous new experiments and initiatives in governance and administration, is continuously striving to make its administration citizen-centric, transparent, efficient, responsive, accountable, and corruption-free. To this end, several laws and government decisions, such as the e-Governance Policy, the Right to Information Act, the One Window Scheme, the Lokayukta System, the Aaple Sarkar Kendra, the Public Service Guarantee Act, and citizen feedback, have been implemented to promote administrative reforms. As part of these administrative reforms, it can be seen that the Maharashtra government is effectively implementing e-governance by prioritizing administrative innovation, excellence, and good governance.

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